

Polarization dependent photoluminescence and optical anisotropy in CuPt_B -ordered dilute $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x$ alloys

Cite as: J. Appl. Phys. 128, 195106 (2020); doi: 10.1063/5.0030091

Submitted: 18 September 2020 · Accepted: 2 November 2020 ·

Published Online: 19 November 2020

Tadas Paulauskas,^{1,a)} Bronislovas Čechavičius,¹ Vytautas Karpus,¹ Lukas Jočionis,¹ Saulius Tumėnas,¹ Jan Devenson,¹ Vaidas Pačebutas,¹ Sandra Stanionytė,¹ Viktorija Strazdienė,¹ Andrejus Geižutis,¹ Mária Čaplovičová,² Viliam Vretenár,² Michael Walls,³ and Arūnas Krotkus¹

AFFILIATIONS

¹Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Saulėtekio al. 3, Vilnius 10257, Lithuania

²STU Centre for Nanodiagnosics, Slovak University of Technology, Vazovova 5, Bratislava 811 07, Slovakia

³Solid State Physics Laboratory, University of Paris-SUD, Bâtiment 510, Orsay 91405, France

^{a)}Author to whom correspondence should be addressed: tadas.paulauskas@ftmc.lt

ABSTRACT

The $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x$ semiconductor alloy allows one to achieve large bandgap reduction and enhanced spin-orbit splitting energy at dilute Bi quantities. The bismide is currently being developed for near- to mid-infrared lasers, multi-junction solar cells, and photodetectors. In this structure-property relationship study of GaAsBi alloys, we report polarization dependent photoluminescence that reaches a polarization ratio up to 2.4 at room temperature. Polarization dependence is also presented using transmittance spectra, birefringence, and linear dichroism. The optical anisotropy observations agree with the predictions of point symmetry reduction in the CuPt_B -type ordered GaAsBi phase. The structural ordering is investigated experimentally from the atomic scale in molecular-beam epitaxy (MBE) grown samples on exact and miscut (001) GaAs substrates, as well as on (001) Ge. The latter sample is composed of anti-phase domains in which the ordering axes are rotated by 90° angles. Since the conditions stabilizing the CuPt_B ordered phase fall within the typical MBE growth regime of dilute bismides, the optical anisotropy in GaAsBi alloys is expected to be ubiquitous. These findings are important for the future development of GaAsBi-based optoelectronics and also provide new means to analyze structurally complex bismide alloys.

© 2020 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0030091>

I. INTRODUCTION

The dilute $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x$ alloy is thus far the most extensively investigated material among Bi-containing III-V semiconductors.^{1,2} Incorporation of large Bi atoms into the lattice produces perturbations mainly to the valence band states, which leads to the bandgap bowing, as well as large spin-orbit band splitting. The interest in this alloy arises from its potential and already implemented applications in near- to mid-infrared range optoelectronics, lasers, photodetectors, and solar cells.¹ Despite wide-scale physical properties investigations of bismides, only rather recently, in the early 2010s, were the first reports made on the observation of spontaneous CuPt -type atomic ordering in GaAsBi.^{3,4}

The CuPt -type atomic ordering in conventional III-V alloys, most notably in $\text{Ga}_x\text{In}_{1-x}\text{P}$ and $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x$, is well known from its discovery in the late 1980s.⁵ Experimentally confirmed effects arising from such modulations include bandgap reduction, valence band splitting, polarization of photoluminescence, birefringence, effective-mass anisotropy, and anisotropic strain.⁵⁻⁹ It is widely accepted that the CuPt -ordering results from surface reconstructions during epitaxial growth, and the (2×1) reconstruction, which is considered to be a prerequisite for the ordering, is also observed in bismides.¹⁰⁻¹²

A perfectly CuPt_B -type ordered zinc-blende $\text{AB}_{0.5}\text{C}_{0.5}$ alloy is a superlattice of alternating AB and AC monolayers on $(\bar{1}11)$ or $(1\bar{1}1)$ planes, conventionally termed as B_+ and B_- subvariants. Ordering

on the other two planes, (111) and $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$, is termed CuPt_A-type but is rarely observed in practice. The CuPt_B ordering occurs in domains with no preference for B₊ and B₋ subvariants if an epitaxial layer is grown on an exact (001) substrate. A single subvariant can be stabilized by employing (001) wafers with a low-angle offcut toward $[\bar{1}10]$. This typically leads to larger ordered domains, and a single subvariant ordering has also been confirmed in GaAsBi.^{13,14} The ordering is never perfect and is quantified by the ordering parameter η . A partially ordered alloy AB_{1-x}C_x can be described as AB_{1-(x- η /2)}C_{x- η /2} and AB_{1-(x+ η /2)}C_{x+ η /2} monolayers on $(\bar{1}11)$ or $(1\bar{1}1)$ planes, with a maximal value of ordering parameter $\eta_{\max} = \min[2x, 2(1-x)]$.

The ordered conventional III-V alloys have been predominantly investigated at the commensurate compositions $x \approx 0.5$ where the ordering parameter can approach unity. On the other hand, dilute bismides are typically synthesized at Bi concentrations close to $x \approx 0.05$. An expected value of the ordering parameter is thus one order of magnitude lower, $\eta \sim 0.1$, than in the conventional semiconductors. Another distinctive feature of bismides is that epitaxial GaAsBi layers are grown compressively strained due to a lattice mismatch with GaAs substrates, while the conventional ordered III-V alloys are usually deposited on lattice-matched substrates, namely, GaInP on GaAs and GaAsSb on InP.

These features make the ordering analysis in dilute strained alloys a difficult task, which may be a reason for the lack of publications investigating relationships between the ordering and physical properties in bismides. Previous studies of the atomic ordering of bismides focused primarily on their atomic and microstructure analysis.¹³⁻¹⁷ The present article examines the influence of the ordering on GaAsBi optoelectronic properties. This is the first study that reports the optical anisotropy in GaAsBi alloys. This article is organized as follows. First, the experimental methods are described. Then, a comprehensive structural analysis of the investigated bismide samples is presented. Polarized photoluminescence (PL) and spectroscopic ellipsometry results are then reported and discussed in regard to theoretical predictions for an ordered alloy. The article ends with the summary and outlook.

II. EXPERIMENT

Samples S1–S5 were grown using a solid source Veeco GENxplor MBE system, equipped with a Veeco As valved cracker and a conventional Dual Filament bismuth source. Semi-insulating GaAs substrates (AXT, Inc.) were employed. The substrate temperature was controlled by a thermocouple (TC) and also monitored with a kSA BandIT broadband pyrometry module (BandIT). The kSA 400 reflection high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED) system was used for *in situ* surface characterization. Each substrate was outgassed at 200 °C in the load-lock and afterward at 300 °C in the buffer chamber. The removal of native oxide was performed at 600–620 °C (BandIT reading) under As₂ flux $\sim 5 \times 10^{-6}$ Torr beam equivalent pressure (BEP). Samples S1–S5 included a nominally 100 nm thick standard-grown GaAs buffer layer. Growth of a GaAsBi layer in samples S1–S5 was performed at 400 °C (TC reading), which corresponded to ~ 310 °C BandIT reading. The initial conditions for GaAsBi layer growth in all samples (S1–S6) were first set by observing in RHEED surface reconstruction transitions on a calibration GaAs wafer at around

600 °C. At such conditions, it was assumed that the III/V atomic flux ratio was close to unity. To maintain the stoichiometry conditions for the growth of bismides, the flux of As₂ was reduced by closing the As cracker valve aperture by 1–2 mils. The bismide layer growth rate in all samples was kept at ~ 500 nm/h. The bismide sample S1 was deposited using Bi BEP 6.0×10^{-8} Torr. The GaAsBi layer in S3 was grown at the Bi BEP of 7.6×10^{-8} Torr, while samples S2, S4, and S5 were grown by keeping identically Bi BEP at 6.7×10^{-8} Torr. Incorporation of Bi in the lattice could be influenced by the distinct substrate offcut angles. Sample S6 was synthesized using an SVT-A MBE chamber equipped with the same sources and As cracker as in the Veeco chamber. A p-type exact (001) Ge substrate (AXT, Inc.) was employed, and native oxides from the substrate were removed at 640 °C (TC). The first part of the GaAs buffer layer, approximately 5 nm thick, was grown at 400 °C using migration-enhanced epitaxy. The substrate temperature was then increased to 500 °C and a further 50 nm of GaAs buffer was deposited. The GaAsBi layer was grown at 350 °C (TC) with the Bi/Ga ratio 0.35–0.37.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were acquired by a Rigaku Smartlab diffractometer equipped with 9 kW rotating Cu anode X-ray generator (K $_{\alpha 1}$ line), scintillation detector SC-70, and a linear Dtex/Ultra detector. Reciprocal-space mapping (RSM) of (004) and (115) reflections was used to evaluate layer relaxations, lattice parameters, and Bi concentrations, using lattice constants GaAs = 5.653 Å and GaBi = 6.324 Å. Superlattice $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ -type reflections were acquired in a skew-symmetric configuration.

An aberration-corrected JEOL-JEM ARM200CF scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM) operated at 200 kV was used for imaging. Probe convergence semi-angle was set to 22 mrad, and high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector inner and outer semi-angles were set to 90 and 370 mrad, respectively. For low-angle annular dark-field (LAADF), the inner and outer detector semi-angles were 40 and 160 mrad, respectively. Additional imaging was performed in a Nion Ultrastem 200 operating at 100 kV with a probe semi-angle of 32 mrad and HAADF detector semi-angles of 70 and 200 mrad. All data were processed with Gatan Digital Micrograph GMS3. Cross-sectional lamella samples, nominally 20–25 nm thick, were prepared using focused-ion beam (FEI Helios Nanolab 650).

Sample-surface morphologies were characterized by atomic-force microscopy (AFM), using a Dimension 3100 SPM system with a Nanoscope IVa controller (Veeco Instruments Inc., USA). Multiple sample areas $\sim 1.5 \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}^2$ in size were scanned. Surface morphology and elemental composition were also examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, FEI HELIOS Nanolab 650) equipped with an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDX) from Oxford Instruments.

Photoluminescence measurements were carried out using a DPSS laser (532 nm) as an excitation source, with the intensity kept at ~ 5 kW/cm², a 0.4 m monochromator SPM-2, and a thermoelectrically cooled InGaAs photodetector. To minimize polarization effects of the monochromator grating, the sample axes $[110]$ and $[\bar{1}10]$ were rotated relative to the monochromator slit by 45°. The Glan-Taylor prism with an extinction ratio of $< 5 \times 10^{-6}$ was used as a polarization analyzer placed in front of the monochromator slit. Low-temperature PL spectra were measured by mounting samples on the cold finger of a liquid nitrogen cryostat.

The polarized transmittance spectra and spectra of normalized Mueller-matrix components were recorded with a dual rotating-compensator ellipsometer RC2 (J.A. Woollam Co., Inc.) at the normal light incidence. After calibration, a straight-through measurement of a Mueller matrix in the air was performed. All recorded Mueller-matrix components were found to be within 0.005 of the ideal value. The linear in-plane birefringence and linear dichroism spectra were determined from the experimental Mueller-matrix spectra by the analytic inversion method.¹⁸

III. ATOMIC STRUCTURE ANALYSIS

A. Sample characterization

Six GaAsBi samples, labeled S1–S6, were grown for this study, all epitaxially deposited by MBE (see Sec. II for more details). Samples S1–S3 were deposited on exact (001) GaAs substrates, while GaAs substrates with 2° and 6° offcuts toward the $[\bar{1}10]$ were used for samples S4 and S5, respectively. An exact (001) Ge substrate was employed for sample S6, which also included a nominally 50 nm thick GaAs buffer layer deposited on Ge. The sample information is summarized in Table I.

X-ray diffraction (004) reflection rocking-curve (XRD-RC) measurements were used to examine the structural quality of the bismide layers and determine their thickness [see Fig. 1(a)]. As can be seen from the sharp peaks and resolved thickness fringes, high-quality epitaxial layers were achieved in samples S1–S5. XRD reciprocal-space mapping (RSM) showed that samples S1–S4 were fully biaxially compressively strained to GaAs substrates, while sample S5 showed ~2% lattice relaxation. GaAsBi is known to be resilient to lattice relaxation and layers well in excess of the critical thickness for dislocation nucleation are often observed.^{2,19} XRD-RSM was not performed on S6 since the sample was of polycrystalline nature.

The bismuth concentrations are presented in Table I. These values were obtained using XRD-RSM (004) and (115) reflection measurements and accounted for lattice relaxation, substrate offcut angle, and any additional epitaxial layer tilt.¹³ The bandgap values E_g listed in Table I are based on the room-temperature band edge PL peak positions. Sample surfaces were examined using atomic-force microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Surface roughness values, obtained using AFM scans of multiple sample areas, are shown in Table I and indicate high surface quality of the S1–S5 samples. Sample S6 surface was rough and showed a high density of Bi droplets. Apart from S6, only S2 had surface droplets with a size of about 50 nm, albeit with a low

density of less than one particle per μm^2 . The droplets on S2 were found to be composed of Ga, as was determined using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Sample S5, on the other hand, displayed circular pits with a size of 50–80 nm and a density of $\sim 2\mu\text{m}^{-2}$. Among samples S1–S5, only S3 displayed phase-separated GaAs-like domains within the bismide layer. The domains were planar-shaped and randomly distributed in the bulk, as was revealed by cross-sectional STEM.^{3,14} The phase separation could be associated with higher surface roughness in S3. High-resolution STEM and STEM-EDX of the bismide layers showed no Bi segregation in S1–S5. We note that no structural features, either within a sample bulk or on the surface, were identified that may render optical anisotropy reported in this study.^{20–22} This leaves atomic-scale configurational effects to be responsible for the optical anisotropy. Atomic-scale sample characterization and XRD CuPt-ordering measurements are presented next.

B. Atomic ordering

So-called skew-symmetric XRD-RC measurements were performed to probe the presence of $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ -type superlattice reflections associated with CuPt-type ordering.²³ Figures 1(b)–1(d) provide representative XRD-RC data of samples S1, S4, and S6. The measurements on samples S1–S3, which were grown on exact (001) GaAs substrates, showed both $\frac{1}{2}(\bar{1}11)$ and $\frac{1}{2}(1\bar{1}1)$ reflections, indicating B₊ and B₋ subvariants of CuPt ordering in the samples [see the representative Fig. 1(b)]. The peak intensities were slightly larger in the thicker sample S1. The samples grown on low-angle offcut GaAs substrates, S4 and S5, demonstrated [Fig. 1(c)] only the $\frac{1}{2}(\bar{1}11)$ reflection, suggesting that a single subvariant CuPt_B ordering is stabilized. The sample S6, deposited on an exact (001) Ge substrate over a thin GaAs buffer layer, manifested the $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ -type superlattice reflections for all four measurement geometries [Fig. 1(d)]. This, however, does not imply that both CuPt_B and CuPt_A coexist in this sample. Instead, sample S6 is composed of anti-phase domains in which the CuPt_B ordering axes $[\bar{1}11]$ and $[1\bar{1}1]$ are rotated by 90° angles, as will be shown below using STEM data.

Sample S4 grown on a 2° offcut substrate manifested the largest intensity of superlattice reflections. We note that no MBE growth optimizations were undertaken for the investigated samples to maximize the CuPt-type ordering. Our previous atomically resolved STEM-EDX ordering parameter evaluation yielded a $\eta = 0.07$ value for a sample with 5.5% Bi.^{13,14} Although the ordering

TABLE I. Parameters of investigated samples: the type of substrate, GaAsBi layer thickness d , bismuth concentration, room-temperature bandgap E_g , and sample-surface roughness R_q . GaAs substrate offcut angles are indicated for samples S4 and S5.

Sample	Substrate	d (nm)	Bi (%)	E_g (eV)	R_q (nm)
S1	GaAs (001)	485	3.4	1.15	0.3
S2	GaAs (001)	192	4.8	1.08	0.4
S3	GaAs (001)	190	5.2	1.04	1.5
S4	GaAs (001) 2°	186	5.0	1.06	0.3
S5	GaAs (001) 6°	180	4.5	1.09	0.5
S6	Ge (001)/GaAs buffer	500	4.6	1.05	>5

FIG. 1. (a) X-ray diffraction rocking-curve (004) reflections showing high-quality S1–S5 samples with distinct thickness fringes. Sample S6 is more defective. (b)–(d) Skew-symmetric XRD measurements of four $\frac{1}{2}(111)$ -type superlattice reflections. Samples S1 and S4 show CuPt_B ordering on two and one B-type planes, respectively. Sample S6 manifests superlattice reflections for all four measurement geometries.

parameters for the present S1–S6 samples were not examined by EDX, one can expect them to be of the order of $\eta \sim 0.1$.

Atomic-scale cross-sectional structural investigations of S1–S6 samples were performed using aberration-corrected STEM. High- and low-angle annular dark-field (HAADF and LAADF) images were acquired along $[110]$ and $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ zone axes. The scanning directions in all images (see Figs. 2 and 3) were aligned such that the growth axis was vertical and directed toward the top of the page. The CuPt_B-type ordering was detected in STEM images only along the $[110]$ zone axis since the ordered $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$ and $(1\bar{1}\bar{1})$ planes are then viewed edge-on. Bismuth-containing columns can be well distinguished in HAADF images due to their higher contrast, as Bi atoms scatter probe electrons much more strongly than Ga or As atoms. A representative HAADF image of the GaAsBi samples S4–S5, deposited on offcut GaAs substrates, is shown in Fig. 2(a) and indicates a single subvariant CuPt_{B+} ordering. The intensity modulations along the

$[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ direction are clearly visible. A Fourier transform (FT) of the image shows a single pair of superlattice $\frac{1}{2}(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$ reflections confirming the XRD result that a single subvariant ordering is predominant. Figure 2(b) shows a representative HAADF image of the GaAsBi samples S1–S3 grown on exact (001) GaAs substrates. The CuPt_B ordering here occurs in the form of randomly dispersed varying size B_+ and B_- domains. This is confirmed by the FT of the image [inset in Fig. 2(b)], which shows two pairs of superlattice $\frac{1}{2}(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$ and $\frac{1}{2}(1\bar{1}\bar{1})$ reflections.

Next, sample S6 is examined, which together with S1–S5, was used in the optical anisotropy analysis. This sample provides an additional test for ordering-induced optical effects because it contains domains whose CuPt-type ordering axes are rotated in a well-defined manner. A low-magnification LAADF image of the sample is shown in Fig. 2(c) with indicated Ge substrate, GaAs buffer, GaAsBi layer, and a protective Pt cap. Sample S6 is comprised of

Downloaded from http://pubs.aip.org/jap/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.5030091/15256468/195106_1_online.pdf

FIG. 2. STEM cross-sectional sample analysis. (a) and (b) Atomic-resolution HAADF images of GaAsBi sample S4 grown on offcut substrates and sample S1 grown on exact GaAs substrates. (c) Low-magnification LAADF image of sample S6 showing numerous anti-phase boundaries indicated by yellow dashed lines. (d) Atomic-resolution HAADF image of S6 near a kinked $\{110\}$ -type anti-phase boundary. Note the reversal of dumbbell polarity across the boundary.

anti-phase domains (APDs), the boundaries of which are marked by dashed vertical yellow lines. The APDs arise in the GaAs buffer layer epitaxially grown on the (001) Ge substrate due to mixed nucleation of Ga and As atoms on the non-polar Ge surface.^{13,24} As the growth proceeds, GaAs grains coalesce forming anti-phase boundaries (APB), which then propagate into the epitaxial GaAsBi layer. Statistically equal amounts of either type of APDs nucleated from Ga or As atoms occur in this sample. Reasonably regular-sized 100–400 nm wide columnar APDs are seen with predominant

$\{110\}$ -type interface planes. A representative GaAsBi APB is shown in the HAADF image [Fig. 2(d)], where Bi atoms are seen to segregate along a kinked $\{110\}$ -type boundary. A closer look shows that a polarity of group-III and group-V columns is reversed in the two crystallites. This can be seen by noting a polarity of the closely spaced atomic columns, so-called “dumbbells,” oriented along the growth direction. Group-V columns with Bi in them are positioned on the top of each dumbbell in the right-hand side grain and are on the bottom in the left-hand one.

FIG. 3. (a) Image derived from sample S6 HAADF micrograph near anti-phase boundary (APB) using pairs of $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ reflections, which are seen in the Fourier transform inset. (b) Atomic model of the APB region.

A region containing two GaAsBi APDs near the GaAs buffer layer is shown in Fig. 3(a). The figure was produced from a HAADF image of S6 sample by applying two pairs of circular masks on the superlattice $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ -type and $\frac{1}{2}\{\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}\}$ -type reflections, shown in the FT inset. CuPt_B-type ordering is thereby highlighted in the left-hand side GaAsBi grain, while no ordering can be seen on the right-hand side, since [001] polarity reversal results in a rotation of B₊ and B₋ domains by a 90° angle around the vertical growth axis. The CuPt_B ordered planes in such rotated domains are not viewed edge-on and thus are not visible in the HAADF image. To clarify the reversal, an atomic model of the APB is shown in Fig. 3(b) with the crystallographic directions conforming to those indicated in Fig. 3(a). Note that the rotation of a tetrahedral unit in GaAs in the left-hand side domain by 180° around the in-plane $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ axis exchanges the CuPt_B-type ordering $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ and $[1\bar{1}\bar{1}]$ axes with the $[111]$ and $[\bar{1}\bar{1}\bar{1}]$ ones. The latter two are conventionally associated with the CuPt_A-type ordering. The same exchange can be achieved by rotating a tetrahedron by a 90° angle around the [001] direction. Similarly, the directionality of (2×1) surface reconstruction units is rotated by a 90° angle with respect to an adjacent domain. This also explains the XRD observation of four $\frac{1}{2}\{111\}$ -type superlattice reflections in S6.

IV. OPTICAL SPECTROSCOPY

A. Scheme of optical transitions

The spontaneous CuPt-type ordering in the conventional zinc-blende alloys and its influence on their electronic structure and optical properties has been extensively studied by Zunger, Wei, Mascarenhas, Zhang, and others.^{5,6,8,25} The CuPt-type ordering

changes the cubic zinc-blende point symmetry T_d to the trigonal C_{3v} one. The perturbative part of the Hamiltonian, describing an influence of the ordering, has the same form as that of the uniaxial strain along the ordering direction,²⁵ namely, the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ axis for the CuPt_{B+} subvariant. For illustrative purposes, Fig. 4(a) shows a depiction of a single subvariant ordered GaAsBi slab (note that in reality Bi concentration in bismides is dilute). The ordering-induced rhombohedral potential splits the degenerate heavy- and light-hole bands $[(hh, lh)$, see Fig. 4(b)] with a magnitude of the valence band (vb) splitting $\Delta = \Delta_c$. If the vb splitting exceeds the thermal energy, $\Delta > k_B T$, the photoluminescence will be determined by the $E_{0,1}$ optical transitions to the upper, hh, vb branch.

Due to the ordering-induced changes in zinc-blende point symmetry, the PL intensity should be polarization dependent for light propagation along the sample-surface normal [001]. The $E_{0,1}$ optical transitions between the conduction and hh bands can be induced by the light with electric vector perpendicular to the ordering direction, $E \perp [\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$. (The $E_{0,2}$ optical transitions between the conduction band and the lower vb branch, lh, occur for $E \parallel [\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ polarization only.) Therefore, the PL polarization dependence for surface-normal light propagation will be determined by a variation of the projection of the E -vector onto the B₊ ordering plane $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$. The PL intensity should be maximal for $E \parallel [110]$ polarization and minimal for $E \parallel [\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$. This is because the $[110]$ direction lies in the $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$ plane, while the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ direction projects onto the $(\bar{1}\bar{1}1)$ plane with the largest angle $\gamma = \arccos(1/\sqrt{3})$ [see Fig. 4(a)]. Therefore, the polarized-PL ratio theoretically is $R = I_{[110]}/I_{[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]} = 3$. When a bismide layer is grown on a GaAs substrate miscut toward the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ direction, the $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ ordering axis rotates further away from the sample-surface normal. The PL

FIG. 4. (a) Atomic structure of CuPt_B -type ordered GaAsBi. (b) Scheme of optical transitions near the fundamental bandgap in unstrained GaAsBi with the CuPt_B -type ordering effect.

polarization ratio becomes $R = 3/[1 + \sqrt{2}\sin(2\theta) + \sin^2\theta]$, which is 2.7 and 2.3 for typical 2° and 6° offcuts, respectively.⁶

The normal-PL polarization dependence can be suppressed by epitaxial strain, which also lifts the vb degeneracy of zinc-blende semiconductors due to strain-induced vb splitting, Δ_e . However, the strained layer becomes optically uniaxial with the optical axis perpendicular to the layer. Hence, in the presence of epitaxial strain and in the absence of ordering, no polarization dependence is expected for normal light propagation. Therefore, in a general case, when both the CuPt -ordering and epitaxial strain are present, the normal-PL polarization dependence is expected to occur when the ordering-induced splitting is of the same order or larger than that due to epitaxial strain, $\Delta_c \gtrsim \Delta_e$.

B. Polarized photoluminescence

The polarized-PL measurements along a sample-surface normal were performed at room (RT, 300 K) and liquid nitrogen (80 K) temperatures. Representative PL spectra of samples S1, S4, and S6 are shown in Fig. 5. The width and shape of PL peaks seen here is typical for GaAsBi alloys and reflects Bi-induced localized states near the vb edge.²⁶ Bismides also manifest pronounced exciton localization effects in the temperature dependence of PL.^{27–29} A typical PL feature is the so-called “s-shape,” whereby the PL peak energy exhibits a blue-red-blue shift with decreasing sample temperature. It usually occurs in the temperature range 30–140 K and is explained by exciton hopping and trapping among two-component localized density of states, one extending from the vb edge and the second displaced some 100 meV into the bandgap.^{13,30} The PL intensity of GaAsBi with increasing Bi concentration tends to be weaker and PL spectra become noisier. This is also evident in the PL of sample S6 whose lattice is composed of APDs.

As seen in Fig. 5, the samples grown on GaAs substrates consistently show higher intensity for the $E \parallel [110]$ polarization as compared to the $E \parallel [\bar{1}10]$ one, while no polarization dependence

is observed for sample S6. Since S6 is composed of crystallites whose ordering B-axes are rotated in-plane by a 90° , no polarization dependence is expected. Photoluminescence polarizations parallel to directions 45° and 135° from $[110]$ were also tested, showing the same PL intensities for all samples S1–S6. The observed PL polarization dependence agrees with theoretical predictions for CuPt_B -type ordered layers.

The RT polarized-PL ratio $R = I_{[110]}/I_{[\bar{1}10]}$ in samples S1–S5 is in the range 1.6–2.4. At liquid nitrogen temperature, R values remain in a similar range of about 1.5–1.9. We note that the PL spectra at 80 K show a complex inner structure associated with the “s-shape” region, so determination of the polarized-PL ratios could be inaccurate at this temperature. There are several reasons why the observed $R \sim 2$ parameter may deviate from the theoretical. First, the $R = 3$ value corresponds to unstrained epitaxial layers. As mentioned above, in the presence of epitaxial strain, the polarization dependence is expected to decrease. Also, at RT the $E_{0,2}$ optical transitions can still occur and would tend to decrease the R value. Other factors such as excitonic band edge transitions and the size of ordered domains could likewise influence the polarization ratio and require further study.⁶

Considering that large epitaxial vb splitting, as compared to an ordering-induced one, would tend to suppress the R value, it is instructive to examine their possible magnitudes. The strains and epitaxial splitting Δ_e in the bismide layers can be easily calculated for given values of elastic constants $C_{12}/C_{11} = 0.46$ and the deformation potential $b = -2$ eV, which for dilute GaAsBi can be taken to be equal to those of GaAs.^{31,32} The calculated epitaxial splitting is about $\Delta_e \sim 45$ meV at the Bi concentration $x = 0.05$. Therefore, the ordering-induced splitting in the investigated dilute bismide samples should be of the order $\Delta_c \sim 40$ meV or more.

Experimentally, one measures the total vb splitting, Δ , which for epitaxially strained and ordered layers is comprised of the partial Δ_e and Δ_c ones. The relation between Δ and the partial splittings was examined numerically by Wei and Zunger in GaInP

FIG. 5. Polarized-PL spectra of selected samples at room (a)–(c) and liquid nitrogen (d)–(f) temperatures.

alloys in the case of small spin-orbit splitting (Δ_e , $\Delta_c \sim \Delta_{s-o}$).²⁵ Although no analytic relationship was explicitly reported in the study, one can see that $\Delta \sim (\Delta_c^2 + \Delta_e^2)^{1/2}$ closely holds for Δ_c associated with $\eta = 0, 0.5, 1.0$ order parameters and a range of Δ_e values (see e.g., Fig. 5 in Ref. 25). In the limiting case of large spin-orbit splitting (Δ_e , $\Delta_c \ll \Delta_{s-o}$), which is relevant for bismides, our preliminary investigations suggest that the total vb splitting is related to the partial ones in the same manner.³³ However, analysis of the relationship is beyond the scope of this study.

Making use of the above square root expression and the experimental $\Delta \sim 60$ meV values of our samples, which were deduced from transmission measurements (see Subsection IV C), one obtains $\Delta_c \sim 40$ meV estimate. The ordering-induced splitting $\Delta_c \sim 40$ meV in bismides is large, as compared to its value in the conventional semiconductors. Indeed, Δ_c in CuPt_B ordered Ga_{0.5}In_{0.5}P alloys is predicted to be only ~ 2 meV at the ordering parameter $\eta = 0.1$.³⁴

C. Spectroscopic ellipsometry

Figures 6(a)–6(c) present the normal-incidence transmittance, T , and optical density, $A = \ln(T^{-1})$, spectra of representative samples, S1, S3, and S4, grown on GaAs substrates. Transmission geometry is chosen for these samples, as the GaAs bandgap is above that of the bismide layers. As can be seen, T exhibits polarization dependence in the vicinity of GaAsBi bandgap energy. The transmittance is systematically higher for $E \parallel [110]$, in accordance

with the results of polarized-PL measurements and with what is expected in a CuPt-ordered alloy. The arrows in Figs. 6(a)–6(c) indicate the spectral positions of the $E_{0,1}$ and $E_{0,2}$ critical points, which were determined from the positions of peaks in the optical density differential spectra, $dA/dh\nu$, presented in Figs. 6(d)–6(f). At the $E \parallel [110]$ polarization, the optical density experiences a sharp increase at photon energies of about 1.17, 1.06, and 1.07 eV for samples S1, S3, and S4, respectively, which coincide with the spectral positions of the PL peaks (see E_g values in Table I) with an accuracy of a few percent. At the $E \parallel [\bar{1}10]$ polarization, a sharp increase of optical density begins at higher photon energies: 1.23, 1.12, and 1.13 eV (for S1, S3, and S4, respectively), which correspond to onsets of the $E_{0,2}$ optical transitions from the lower vb branch to the conduction band. This phenomenological determination of the $E_{0,1}$ and $E_{0,2}$ energies from spectral positions of peaks in optical density derivative spectra allows to estimate the vb splitting, $\Delta = E_{0,2} - E_{0,1}$. We find it in samples S1–S5 to be of about $\Delta \sim 60$ meV, which agrees with previous measurements in bismides.^{35–37}

To check the influence of atomic ordering on the optoelectronic properties, we have carried out Mueller-matrix spectroscopic ellipsometry measurements of the birefringence $\Delta n = n_{[110]} - n_{[\bar{1}10]}$ and linear dichroism $\Delta \kappa = \kappa_{[110]} - \kappa_{[\bar{1}10]}$. The experimental results obtained are presented in Figs. 6(g)–6(i). The Δn and $\Delta \kappa$ spectra manifest a Lorentzian-type dispersion centered at the photon energies of the $E_{0,1}$ and $E_{0,2}$ optical transitions, clearly indicating polarization dependent refractive index.³⁸ Any possible higher energy features in these spectra are obscured due to absorption in GaAs substrates.

FIG. 6. Transmission-mode spectroscopic ellipsometry data of selected samples S1, S3, and S4. (a)–(c) Transmittance (full curves) and optical density (dashed curves) spectra at the $E \parallel [110]$ and $E \parallel [\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ polarizations. (d)–(f) Optical density differential spectra. (g)–(i) Birefringence $\Delta n = n_{[110]} - n_{[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]}$ and linear dichroism $\Delta\kappa = \kappa_{[110]} - \kappa_{[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]}$ spectra.

As can be seen from Fig. 6, the bismides manifesting both B_+ and B_- subvariants of CuPt_B ordering (samples S1–S3 grown on exact GaAs substrates) and the bismides with single B_+ subvariant (S4–S5 grown on offcut GaAs) show qualitatively similar optical anisotropy. To explain the result, further investigation is needed. However, note that in layers on exact GaAs substrates, both B_+ and B_- ordering axes, $[\bar{1}\bar{1}1]$ and $[1\bar{1}\bar{1}]$, constitute the same angle with a (001) sample surface and project onto the same in-plane direction, $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ or $[1\bar{1}0]$. We thus expect the polarization anisotropy at the normal light propagation to be insensitive to B_+ and B_- ordering subvariants.

The transmission-mode spectroscopic ellipsometry measurements of transmittance and birefringence-dichroism spectra are comparatively easy to perform and can be used as a test for the presence of CuPt -type ordering. We have carried out the test on

more than 10 bismide samples MBE-grown under various growth conditions and Bi concentrations (not shown here), with the result that all of them manifested polarization anisotropy. This preliminary observation suggests that the spontaneous atomic ordering in bismides is widespread.

V. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

In this work, a structural and optical study of the dilute $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x$ alloys was carried out reporting spontaneous ordering-induced optical anisotropy effects. The epitaxial bismide layers MBE-grown on exact (001) GaAs substrates manifested both B_+ and B_- subvariants of CuPt_B ordering, while the bismides grown on 2° and 6° offcut GaAs showed a single B_+ subvariant. We also analyzed a bismide layer grown on an exact (001) Ge substrate,

which included a GaAs buffer layer. The bismide was shown to be composed of CuPt_B ordered columnar APDs, whose ordering axes are rotated by a 90° angle around the growth axis with respect to adjacent domains.

The optical anisotropy was revealed in samples grown on exact and offcut (001) GaAs substrates via polarized photoluminescence and transmittance spectra, as well as by birefringence and linear dichroism measurements. The observed polarization dependence in all the optical measurements agreed with theoretical predictions for the CuPt_B ordering. No optical anisotropy was observed in the bismide sample composed of APDs, in which the anisotropy is not expected. Multiple sample surface and bulk characterization techniques, including SEM, AFM, XRD, and cross-sectional STEM, were employed to exclude other possible sources of structural anisotropies that may cause these optical effects. Atomic-scale HAADF analysis of Bi atom distribution and XRD suggests that the ubiquitous CuPt_B ordering is responsible for the optical anisotropy. Further work will be needed to clarify the magnitude of the ordering-induced vb splitting in GaAsBi alloys and to better understand the reasons for such pronounced effects at dilute Bi concentrations. Polarization anisotropy is an important factor to consider for the future development of GaAsBi-based lasers and photodetectors. These findings elucidate spontaneous ordering effects in GaAsBi and encourage its further investigations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Xiaoyan Li for her assistance with STEM sample characterization and Arnas Naujokaitis for STEM sample preparation. This work was supported by the European Regional Development Fund (Project No. 01.2.2-LMT-K-718-02-0020) under grant agreement with the Research Council of Lithuania (LMTLT). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 823717-ESTEEM3. This study was also supported by the Operational Program Research and Innovation for the project ITMS2014+ code: 313010T598 co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- ¹S. Wang and O. Lu, *Bismuth-Containing Alloys and Nanostructures* (Springer, 2019).
- ²Z. Batool *et al.*, *Molecular Beam Epitaxy* (Elsevier, 2013), Vol. 139.

- ³A. G. Norman, R. France, and A. J. Ptak, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* **29**, 03C121 (2011).
- ⁴D. F. Reyes, F. Bastiman, C. J. Hunter, D. L. Sales, A. M. Sanchez, J. P. R. David, and D. González, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **9**, 23 (2014).
- ⁵A. Mascarenhas, *Spontaneous Ordering in Semiconductor Alloys* (Springer, 2002).
- ⁶Y. Zhang, A. Mascarenhas, P. Ernst, F. A. J. M. Driessen, D. J. Friedman, K. A. Bertness, J. M. Olson, C. Geng, F. Scholz, and H. Schweizer, *J. Appl. Phys.* **81**, 6365 (1997).
- ⁷E. P. O'Reilly and A. T. Meney, *Phys. Rev. B* **51**, 7566 (1995).
- ⁸S.-H. Wei and A. Zunger, *Phys. Rev. B* **57**, 8983 (1998).
- ⁹R. M. France, W. E. McMahon, J. Kang, M. A. Steiner, and J. F. Geisz, *J. Appl. Phys.* **115**, 053502 (2014).
- ¹⁰M. Masnadi-Shirazi, D. A. Beaton, R. B. Lewis, X. Lu, and T. Tiedje, *J. Cryst. Growth* **338**, 80 (2012).
- ¹¹F. Bastiman, A. G. Cullis, J. P. R. David, and S. J. Sweeney, *J. Cryst. Growth* **341**, 19 (2012).
- ¹²J. Occena, T. Jen, H. Lu, B. A. Carter, T. S. Jimson, A. G. Norman, and R. S. Goldman, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **113**, 211602 (2018).
- ¹³T. Paulauskas *et al.*, *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 1 (2020).
- ¹⁴T. Paulauskas *et al.*, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* **15**, 121 (2020).
- ¹⁵A. Beyer, N. Knaub, P. Rosenow, K. Jandieri, P. Ludewig, L. Bannow, S. W. Koch, R. Tonner, and K. Volz, *Appl. Mater. Today* **6**, 22 (2017).
- ¹⁶D. L. Sales *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **98**, 101902 (2011).
- ¹⁷M. Wu *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **105**, 041602 (2014).
- ¹⁸O. Arteaga and A. Canillas, *Opt. Lett.* **35**, 559 (2010).
- ¹⁹R. France, C. S. Jiang, and A. J. Ptak, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **98**, 101908 (2011).
- ²⁰E. Luna *et al.*, *J. Appl. Phys.* **117**, 185302 (2015).
- ²¹C. R. Tait, L. Yan, and J. M. Millunchick, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **111**, 042105 (2017).
- ²²K. N. Collar *et al.*, *Nanotechnology* **29**, 035604 (2018).
- ²³Q. Liu, W. Prost, and F. J. Tegude, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **67**, 2807 (1995).
- ²⁴S. A. Ringel, R. M. Sieg, S. M. Ting, and E. A. Fitzgerald, in *Conference Record of 26th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialist Conference* (IEEE, 1997), Vol. 793.
- ²⁵S.-H. Wei and A. Zunger, *Phys. Rev. B* **49**, 14337 (1994).
- ²⁶R. Kudrawiec *et al.*, *J. Appl. Phys.* **106**, 023518 (2009).
- ²⁷D. A. Beaton, A. Mascarenhas, and K. Alberi, *J. Appl. Phys.* **118**, 235701 (2015).
- ²⁸B. Yan *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **114**, 052104 (2019).
- ²⁹S. Imhof *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **98**, 161104 (2011).
- ³⁰T. Wilson *et al.*, *Sci. Rep.* **8**, 6457 (2018).
- ³¹I. Vurgaftman, J. R. Meyer, and L. R. Ram-Mohan, *J. Appl. Phys.* **89**, 5815 (2001).
- ³²V. Karpus *et al.*, *Opt. Express* **26**, 33807 (2018).
- ³³G. L. Bir and G. E. Pikus, *Symmetry and Strain-Induced Effects in Semiconductors* (Wiley, 1974).
- ³⁴Y. Zhang, A. Mascarenhas, and L. W. Wang, *Phys. Rev. B* **63**, 201312 (2001).
- ³⁵S. Francoeur *et al.*, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **82**, 3874 (2003).
- ³⁶F. Dybała, J. Kopaczek, M. Gladysiewicz, E.-M. Pavelescu, C. Romanitan, O. Ligor, A. Arnoult, C. Fontaine, and R. Kudrawiec, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **111**, 192104 (2017).
- ³⁷Z. Batool, K. Hild, T. J. C. Hosea, X. Lu, T. Tiedje, and S. J. Sweeney, *J. Appl. Phys.* **111**, 113108 (2012).
- ³⁸M. Schubert *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. B* **60**, 16618 (1999).